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ARTEMIS User Needs Survey

Museum educators / heritage interpreters Digital Tools, Monitoring Practices, and Data Acquisition

Digital Tools or Technologies

Digital Tools or Technologies used to Evaluate content

Methods for Collecting or Accessing

Challenges in Evaluating content

Museum educators / heritage interpreters Data Types, Formats, and Interoperability Standards

Types of Data

Data Format

Standard or Protocols

Museum educators / heritage interpreters Data Accessibility, Sharing Practices, and Collaboration Platforms

Data Structure and Accessibility

Use of Collaborative Digital Platforms

Main Difficulties in Sharing Data

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Museum educators / heritage interpreters
3D Modelling, Digital Simulations, and Integration of Digital Technologies

Museum educators / heritage interpreters
Digital Twin Applications, Functional Expectations, and Future Adoption

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Museum educators / heritage interpreters

Cross-analysis insights

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TECHNOLOGIES × DATA TYPES	High-resolution images of artworks or artifacts	Audio and video materials (interviews, documentaries, narration)	Textual narratives or historical documents	3D models or reconstructions	Digital maps or interactive timelines	Multilingual or inclusive content	Educational games or gamified content
Interactive digital displays or touchscreens	12	12	10	12	9	6	4
Online learning platforms or virtual tours	11	14	12	11	8	5	4
Augmented Reality (AR) or Virtual Reality (VR) applications	7	8	5	10	5	4	2
Gamified tools or serious games for cultural content	5	7	8	4	4	3	5
Multimedia authoring tools (e.g., Adobe, Canva, video editing software)	14	13	12	13	10	7	3
Mobile apps for storytelling or visitor engagement	8	9	11	7	10	6	3
Social media or web-based storytelling	8	10	10	8	9	4	4
I don't use digital tools	1	1	1	1	1	0	0

TECHNOLOGIES × METHODS	Internal institutional repositories or archives	Open-access databases or aggregators (e.g., Europeana, Wikimedia)	Content created in-house by staff or external contractors	Collaborative projects or partnerships	I do not collect or manage digital content directly
Interactive digital displays or touchscreens	7	12	12	9	0
Online learning platforms or virtual tours	9	16	9	9	2
Augmented Reality (AR) or Virtual Reality (VR) applications	4	8	8	5	1
Gamified tools or serious games for cultural content	3	7	6	5	2
Multimedia authoring tools (e.g., Adobe, Canva, video editing software)	8	13	13	11	0
Mobile apps for storytelling or visitor engagement	5	10	8	8	2
Social media or web-based storytelling	7	13	8	8	0
I don't use digital tools	2	1	2	2	0

MONITORING TOOLS × EVALUATING CHALLENGES

	Lack of appropriate tools or platforms	Difficulty linking digital engagement to actual learning or impact	Low response rates or inconsistent feedback from users	Limited time or staff to conduct evaluations	Unclear evaluation criteria or success indicators	I don't face particular challenges
Multimedia editing software (e.g., video/audio editing, Authoring platforms for interactive content (e.g., H5P, Storyline, Canva))	7	9	5	11	6	0
Online learning platforms (e.g., Moodle, Google Classroom)	5	9	5	11	8	0
Tools for tracking engagement and user analytics (e.g., Google)	4	9	4	10	6	0
Collaborative content creation tools (e.g., Google Docs, Padlet, Survey or feedback tools (e.g., Typeform, Mentimeter))	0	4	3	6	3	0
I do not use digital tools for content creation or evaluation	5	12	7	12	7	0
	2	5	3	7	3	0
	1	1	1	2	1	1

DATA TYPES × FORMATS	Multimedia formats (e.g., JPEG, MP4, WAV)	Presentation and document files (e.g., PDF, DOC, PPT)	3D file formats or models (e.g., OBJ, STL, glTF, point clouds)	Interactive formats (e.g., HTML5, WebGL, H5P)	Structured educational formats (e.g., SCORM, xAPI)
High-resolution images of artworks or artifacts	17	15	8	4	0
Audio and video materials (interviews, documentaries, narration)	17	17	6	4	0
Textual narratives or historical documents	18	16	6	5	0
3D models or reconstructions	16	16	11	4	0
Digital maps or interactive timelines	14	13	6	5	0
Multilingual or inclusive content	8	8	3	3	0
Educational games or gamified content	4	4	3	3	0

COLLABORATIVE PLATFORMS × SHARING DIFFICULTIES

	Compatibility issues between different software and file formats	Lack of clear copyright/licensing policies	Institutional restrictions or approval processes	Limited digital infrastructure for open access publishing	Low collaboration between departments or institutions	I don't encounter any major difficulties
Yes, platforms internal to my institution	2	4	4	3	3	1
Yes, external or open-source platforms (e.g., Padlet, Google Workspace, Trello)	6	6	4	6	7	1
No, but I would be interested in using them	4	3	6	6	7	0
No, I don't see their usefulness	0	0	0	0	1	0

3D MODELS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of training or digital skills	Limited time or resources to develop digital content	Technical complexity or reliability of tools	Resistance from colleagues or institutions	Difficulty engaging specific audiences with digital formats	No particular difficulties
Yes, frequently	7	6	4	3	4	0
Yes, occasionally	4	6	4	2	1	0
No, but I would be interested	6	8	4	4	0	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	1	2	2	0	1	0

3D MODELS × DIGITAL TWIN USE CASE	Offering immersive learning experiences (e.g., virtual tours, simulations)	Supporting inclusive and multilingual engagement	Facilitating collaboration between educators and curators	Enhancing storytelling through real-time data and historical content	Access to otherwise inaccessible or fragile heritage	I do not see relevant applications
Yes, frequently	9	5	6	8	7	1
Yes, occasionally	8	6	3	8	8	0
No, but I would be interested	7	6	5	8	5	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	1	1	2	3	1	0

SIMULATIONS × INTEGRATION CHALLENGES	Lack of training or digital skills	Limited time or resources to develop digital content	Technical complexity or reliability of tools	Resistance from colleagues or institutions	Difficulty engaging specific audiences with digital formats	No particular difficulties
Yes, frequently	6	5	1	3	3	0
Yes, occasionally	6	7	9	3	2	0
No, but I would be interested	5	8	1	3	0	0
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	1	2	3	0	1	0

SIMULATIONS × REACTIVE DIGITAL TWIN SUPPORT	Real-time access to the object's condition and historical context	Predictive models to visualize how objects or sites have changed or will evolve	Simulations to illustrate historical events or transformations	Alerts and updates related to the object/site status or relevance (e.g., anniversaries, risks)	Integration with interpretive content (e.g., narratives, stories, audio)	I'm not sure
Yes, frequently	5	3	7	4	7	0
Yes, occasionally	10	10	7	5	9	0
No, but I would be interested	6	6	5	4	5	1
No, and I don't see the relevance for my work	2	0	1	0	1	0